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“CIRCUITS WITHOUT CLASSROOMS”

Teaching major subjects was extremely difficult during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic. I found teaching online to be a very difficult endeavor as a faculty member at Negros Oriental State University, particularly for major subjects like Electrical Technology. Even though I was handling first-year students, the limitations on in person instruction made it impossible to completely develop their practical abilities through hands-on exercises.

The dedication to education could not be abandoned in spite of these constraints. After all, our students' futures were on the line.

I became aware of the various struggles my students had during my online classes. Many of them hailed from low-income homes, some were unable to purchase the rudimentary devices required for online education. I've heard of students scaling trees in search of a reliable internet connection. I was motivated to think of creative ways to adapt after learning about the hardships they faced.

I urged my students to use the internet to its fullest possible and seek out more materials, especially on platforms like YouTube, in order to expand the lessons. But I also underlined how important it is to use the internet sensibly, urging students to focus on learning materials and stay away from distractions. This approach allowed them to learn more than I could offer in our brief virtual meetings.

To aid in the development of their technical skills, I also urged my students to utilize the online simulation tools that were available. These simulations offered a platform where students could at least explore and apply important concepts virtually, even though they weren't a perfect replacement for practical experience. In order to provide everyone an equal opportunity to finish the necessary tasks, regardless of their individual difficulties, deadlines were loosened. In order to help them with their independent study, I also provided them with extra learning materials and references.

I learned as much from teaching during this period as my students did. It served as a lesson in empathy, fortitude, and creativity. Learning and optimism continued to thrive in a world where the walls of the classroom had vanished.